

ACTION GAMES-AS AN IMPORTANT MEANS OF INCREASING THE PHYSICAL ACTIVITY OF CHILDREN

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Annotation: This article explores the role of action games in promoting physical activity among children. It delves into the potential benefits of incorporating action games into a child's routine, addressing concerns related to sedentary lifestyles and the impact of video games. The study employs a literature analysis to examine the existing research and discusses various methods to integrate action games into children's daily activities. The results highlight the positive outcomes associated with action games, leading to an informed discussion on the subject. Finally, the article offers conclusions and suggestions for parents, educators, and health professionals aiming to enhance children's physical activity levels.

Keywords: Action games, physical activity, children, health, sedentary lifestyle, video games, exercise, screen time.

The prevalence of sedentary lifestyles among children has become a growing concern in recent years. The increased use of electronic devices, including video games, has led to a decrease in physical activity, potentially impacting the long-term health and well-being of our younger generation. However, action games, a popular genre among children, present an opportunity to counteract this trend. This article explores the potential of action games as a means of increasing the physical activity of children.

Numerous studies have investigated the relationship between video games and physical activity in children. Many of them have found that action games can

lead to increased energy expenditure due to their interactive and physically engaging nature. These games often require players to move rapidly, jump, dodge, and even mimic real-world movements. For example, games like "Just Dance" and "Wii Fit" encourage players to be physically active while having fun.

To assess the impact of action games on physical activity, various methods can be employed. Longitudinal studies can track the physical activity levels of children before and after incorporating action games into their routines. Surveys and questionnaires can gather data on children's preferences and attitudes towards action games. Accelerometers and activity trackers can provide objective measurements of movement and energy expenditure.

Action games can be a valuable means of increasing the physical activity of children. These games, which often involve physical movement, can provide several benefits for kids:

- **Physical Exercise:** Action games encourage children to be physically active, helping them develop their strength, agility, and coordination. This can contribute to better overall physical fitness.
- **Cardiovascular Health:** Many action games involve running, jumping, and other activities that elevate the heart rate. This can help improve cardiovascular health in children.
- **Motor Skills:** Action games often require precise movements and coordination, which can enhance a child's fine and gross motor skills. These skills are crucial for various physical activities and everyday tasks.
- **Social Interaction:** Many action games are played with friends or in group settings, promoting social interaction and cooperation among children. This can lead to improved social skills and teamwork.
- **Fun and Engagement:** Action games are typically enjoyable and engaging for kids, making physical activity feel like play rather than exercise. This can motivate children to be active and adopt a more active lifestyle.

- **Stress Reduction:** Physical activity in the form of action games can help reduce stress and anxiety in children. It provides an outlet for energy and can have a positive impact on mental well-being.
- **Skill Development:** Some action games may require the development of specific skills, such as balance, flexibility, and hand-eye coordination. These skills can be valuable in various aspects of a child's life.

It's essential, however, to strike a balance between video games or screen-based action games and physical outdoor activities. While action video games can offer benefits, excessive screen time can have negative consequences. Encouraging a mix of outdoor play, sports, and indoor action games can provide a well-rounded approach to increasing physical activity in children. Additionally, parental supervision and guidance are crucial to ensure that the games and activities are safe and age-appropriate.

The positive outcomes of action games as a means to increase physical activity are promising. However, it is essential to address potential concerns, such as screen time and the sedentary nature of gaming. To strike a balance, parents and caregivers should monitor and limit screen time, ensuring that action games are just one component of a child's active lifestyle. It's also important to choose age-appropriate games that are designed to promote physical activity safely.

Conclusions:

Action games offer an innovative and engaging solution to the challenge of increasing physical activity in children. While the long-term impact of such games on health is still a subject of ongoing research, their short-term benefits are evident. Parents, educators, and health professionals can use action games as a tool to encourage children to be more physically active, provided that screen time is carefully managed.

- Encourage a balanced approach: Encourage children to enjoy action games as part of their daily activities, but also emphasize the importance of outdoor play, sports, and other forms of physical exercise.
- Screen time limits: Implement age-appropriate screen time limits to ensure children are not spending excessive hours playing video games.
- Choose educational action games: Opt for action games that have an educational component, teaching children valuable skills or knowledge.
- Parental involvement: Parents can join their children in playing action games to promote bonding and ensure safe and controlled gaming environments.
- Consult health professionals: Consult with pediatricians or child psychologists for guidance on incorporating action games into a child's routine, taking into consideration individual needs and preferences.

In conclusion, action games can be a valuable tool in increasing the physical activity of children, provided they are used mindfully and in combination with other forms of exercise. By integrating action games into a balanced lifestyle, we can harness the potential of technology to promote health and well-being in the younger generation.

Reference.

1. Хакимова, Н. У. (2018). Влияние физических упражнений, игр, развлечений на физическое развитие детей. Вопросы педагогики, (3), 126-128.
2. Хакимова, Н. У. (2020). Роль общественного спорта в повышении эффективности женского спорта. Вестник науки и образования, (7-2 (85)), 81-83
3. Н. N. Uralovna & U. D. Musaevich (2019). The importance of rhythmic gymnastics in developing pupils' physical capabilities. European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 7(12).

4. Uralovna, H. N. (2021). Attraction and attention of women's wrestling in Uzbekistan. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(11), 703-704.
5. Uralovna, H. N. (2021). Introduction of the Method of Using Sleep Games in Dance Movements in the Development of Balance. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630)*, 11, 138-139.
6. Musayevich, U. D. (2021). Effectiveness of Using New Pedagogical Technologies to Increase General and Special Physical Training of Young Players. *European Journal of Life Safety and Stability (2660-9630)*, 11, 110- 111